

A Framework for Identifying Teacher Competencies of Mathematical Modeling

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With the proposed introduction of a new Primary Mathematics Curriculum in Ireland, mathematical modeling¹ is a pedagogical approach to teaching mathematics that Irish primary school teachers may not be familiar with. This article explores literature in the field that can support teachers in this role and identifies a gap in the educational field of mathematical modeling at primary school level. A proposed framework for identifying teacher competencies of mathematical modeling is presented as means of providing professional development in mathematical modeling.

Introduction

In the midst of reform at primary school level in Ireland and with the proposed introduction of a new Primary Mathematics Curriculum, it is essential that teacher competencies to implement these changes are identified and supported. There are a number of proposed changes from the *Primary Mathematics Curriculum* (PMC) (Department of Education² (DoE), 1999) that are highlighted in the research. One such change is the implementation of meta-practices that teachers should engage with, when teaching mathematics (Dooley et al., 2014, p. 36). These include maths-talk, development of a productive disposition, formative assessment, cognitively challenging tasks and mathematical modeling. While teacher competencies for these meta-practices will need to be established, there appears to be a gap in the literature regarding mathematical modeling at primary school level. This article will explore literature in the area of mathematical modeling at primary school level as well as identifying a proposed framework for identifying teacher competencies. This will be an essential prerequisite to professional development provision as part of the roll out of the new primary mathematics curriculum.

Literature Review

Mathematical Modeling

Mathematical modeling describes the process of developing a model and can begin with a real life problem. Models are simplified representations of reality that allow the application of mathematics (Greefrath & Vorholter, 2016, p.9). During the mathematical modeling process pupils mathematise real world problems in mathematical terms. Single mathematising in the modeling cycle only requires one step to transfer a real life problem to a model whereas complex mathematising requires more than one step. A model presented by

¹ Modelling and Modeling are found in the literature. For the purpose of this paper the later spelling will be used as in Dooley et al., (2014) and its addendum (Dooley, 2019).

² Formally the Department of Education and Science

Blum and Leib (2007) breaks down the modeling process into a number of steps; constructing, simplifying, mathematising, working mathematically, interpreting, validating and exposing. Mathematical modeling can promote the development of mathematical content, process-oriented skills and general life skills for example being critical with data represented in the media or social skills. The duality mathematical modeling plays also needs to be investigated where mathematical modeling itself can develop useful skills and concepts with pupils but can also be a means to learning mathematics.

Systematic Review of the Literature

Stohlmann and Abarraćín (2016) conducted a systematic review of the literature, investigating what studies have been conducted at elementary grades (10 years and under) in mathematical modeling. Mathematical modeling is defined as “an iterative process that involves open-ended, real world, practical problems that students make sense of with mathematics using assumptions, approximations, and multiple representations” (Stohlmann & Abarraćín, 2016, p. 1-2). Twenty-nine publications were included in the study where mathematical modeling content, assessment data, population, unit of analysis and effectiveness data was gathered. Data collected was generally qualitative in nature using audio and video recordings, student work and researcher field notes. Modeling eliciting activities were the most common approach utilised, however, the majority of the studies are by Lyn English who engaged in a three-year longitudinal study and published papers throughout, so this may not be representative of the greater research. One study investigated the learning of heuristics and the metacognitive processes for mathematical applications, emphasising the importance problem solving plays in the mathematical modeling process. Ten of the studies were conducted in Australia, six were in the US and Europe represented seven articles including one from the Irish context. Only four studies included professional development for participating teachers. Ultimately, it was found that young children are capable of mathematical modeling and that they benefit from it greatly.

Problem Solving

Problem solving is an essential part of the mathematical modeling process but also of the PMC (DoE, 1999) where it is described as a skill that needs to be developed with pupils as well as context for developing concepts and skills. Pupils need “to analyse mathematical situations; to plan, monitor and evaluate solutions; to apply strategies; and to demonstrate creativity and self-reliance in using mathematics” to develop higher order skills (DoE, 1999, p. 8). The implementation of mathematical modeling will build on current practices of problem solving in the primary school context.

International Assessments

Ireland’s performance in international assessments such as Trends in Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) portray the progression Ireland has made in mathematics in recent years for example in PISA 2018 the OECD average was 489.3 and Ireland scored 499.6, similar to TIMSS 2019 where Ireland scored 48 points above the centre point. While Ireland has performed particularly well, it is

important to identify where more progress could be made. Sixteen countries significantly outperformed Ireland in PISA 2018 and seven countries in TIMSS 2019 such as China and Singapore. The Education Research Centre (ERC) have highlighted our under performance at higher benchmarks in these international assessments such as PISA 2018 where Ireland achieved 8.2% in the level 5/6 or advanced benchmarks in contrast to Korea who scored 21.4%. Similar findings were highlighted in TIMSS in 2019 where it depicts that only one in seven (15%) of pupils in fourth class achieved the advanced benchmark. Furthermore, McKeown et al., outline that “a number of countries with overall mean scores not significantly different from Ireland’s had proportionately more students at Levels 5-6, including Sweden (12.6%) and the UK (12.9%). In Northern Ireland, 8.3% of students performed at Levels 5-6” (2019, p. 8). Comparable findings were portrayed by the ERC for TIMSS 2019 (Perkins & Clerkins, 2020). TIMSS 2019 reported a relative weakness in the cognitive domain of reasoning (Perkins & Clerkins, 2020).

Considering Ireland’s strong position in international assessments, it is relevant to look at National Assessments of Mathematics and English Reading (NAMER) in Ireland. In a performance report published by the ERC in 2014, it was found that “there is scope for pupils in Second and Sixth classes to improve further on higher level mathematical processes, including Apply & Problem Solve” (Shiel et al., 2014, p. 15). A further context report was published in late 2015 and in an effort to explain possible reasons for challenges in developing higher benchmarks and raising standards to compete with countries that are significantly outperforming Ireland it identified a number of possible areas of concern; “While the nature and focus of mathematics instruction is likely to be a factor, other factors affecting curriculum implementation are also relevant, including support for teachers in the form of professional development, time allocated to teaching mathematics, the quality and appropriateness of support materials such as tests and text books, the support pupils receive at home and at school, and pupils’ dispositions” (Kavanagh et al., 2015, p. 16). Furthermore, problem solving with emphasis on mathematical modeling, realistic contexts and collaboration is emphasised and recommended (p. 17). This forms the basis of a rationale to introduce mathematical modeling into the Irish primary classroom where more realistic mathematics problems may be explored. It will also investigate how professional development can support teachers in implementing this in their classrooms.

Research in the Irish context

In 2014, a research paper was published to support the development of a new Primary Mathematics Curriculum in Ireland (Dooley et al., 2014). Two approaches to mathematical modeling were identified as part of this process; Realistic Maths Education (RME) (van den Heuvel-Panhuizen, 2003) and Lyn English’s longitudinal study in Australia (eg. 2006, 2007, 2008). Dooley re-emphasised these approaches in a further report published in 2019. In the RME approach mathematical modeling can be identified as an organising activity from which a model emerges (Gravemeijer & Stephan, 2002) and deeper, more flexible understandings are generated. The emphasis is on the mathematisation process and the generalisation of models that can be used in a variety of situations. The literature describes the transition in the

modeling process as a model of a situation to a model for thinking about mathematics (Gravemeijer & Stephan, 2002). Content related goals associated with this perspective include solving realistic problems, the development of modeling skills and developing an understanding of the real world. English's approach to mathematical modeling is identified as a means of addressing realistically complex situations where models or conceptual tools are developed. These are needed for a specific purpose or a goal. This could be considered an extension to problem solving currently experienced at primary school. The first stage of this modeling cycle begins with a modeling eliciting activity and progresses to model exploration and model application with related problems. Critical reflection is essential in this process.

While the RME approach to mathematical modeling can be categorised as an organising activity and English and her colleagues' approach can be identified as means of addressing realistically complex situations, both approaches focus on the mathematisation that occurs as part of that process. This will form the basis for the theoretical perspective adopted in this study.

Teacher Competencies in Mathematical Modeling

In the literature, competencies of mathematical modeling are presented, however, teacher competencies required to teach mathematical modeling are limited. One such article published by Ferri and Blum (2009), as part of Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education (CERME 6), explored teacher competencies for mathematical modeling in teacher education. A number of competencies were regarded as important in this research including; theoretical, task related, teaching and diagnostic. Assessment was also mentioned but was not expected from teachers with no experience of it. The seminar was broken down into five parts; theory, practice (tasks), theory and practice, presentations and lastly lesson-reflection (p. 2048). The intention of this research was that students would learn mathematical modeling as well as develop strategies to teach it. Cooperative learning strategies were applied to achieve this where activities such as jigsaw, think-pair-share, round robin brainstorming, silent writing conversations and inside-out-circle were utilised. For teachers engaging in mathematical modeling for the first time it would be essential to become familiar with mathematical modeling competencies through professional development before teacher competencies could be addressed as described above.

Professional Development

In 2020 a report was published from the Education Research Centre (ERC) which outlined "the importance of focusing an evaluation on the core features of effective Teacher Professional Learning (TPL), rather than the mode of delivery or type of activity" (Rawdon et al., 2020. p. 2). *Cosán*, The Natural Framework for Teacher Learning, outlines learning processes that teachers experience during TPL. These include; mentoring/ coaching, practice and collaboration, research, reading and professional contributions, immersive professional activities, and courses, programmes, workshops and other events.

Professional development is an essential part of improving school performance (Hargreaves, 1994) and transformative practices are key for effective change in practice for

teachers (Kennedy, 2005). Collaborative Professional Inquiry models are deemed to be more transformative where teacher agency and autonomy are central. Considering this, a transformative model will be established where “all models and experiences that include an element of collaborative problem identification and subsequent activity, where the subsequent activity involves inquiring into one’s own practice and understanding more about other practice, perhaps through engagement with existing research” (Kennedy, 2014, p. 693).

Guskey’s (2000) five-level evaluation framework includes participants’ reactions; participants’ learning; organisational support and change; participants’ use of new knowledge and skills; and, student learning outcomes. Evaluation at one level is not enough to see change. Guskey’s framework does not include core features of effective TPL which is outlined as an effective means of evaluating and therefore, evaluation would have to focus on the model of CPD which is collaborative professional inquiry. However, conceptual frameworks from Desimone (2009), Merchie et al., (2018) and King (2014) include features of effective TPL. Desimone (2009), evaluation model suggests five main features of effective TPL including; content focus, active learning, coherence, duration and collective participation. This model assumes the material being covered is content related which would have to be adopted for the implementation of mathematical modeling, a meta-practice. Merchie et al., (2018) framework builds on Desimone’s work where it outlines linear stages of professional development including features of the intervention, teacher quality, teacher behaviour and student behaviour. Alongside this, contextual factors as well as teacher and student personal characteristics are included. King (2014), emphasises diffusion of TPL where she speaks of the ripple effect within the system. Schoenfeld (2017), Teaching for Robust Understanding (TRU) Framework, includes five dimensions of powerful classrooms, including; the content, cognitive demand, equitable access to content, agency, ownership and identity, and formative assessment. These are divided into three proficiency levels to assist teachers to reflect on their teaching. The purpose is for professional development as opposed to evaluation of practice. The focus also shifts from the teacher to student learning.

Research Questions

It is intended that this research could support teacher educators and teachers in the implementation of mathematical modeling in Ireland. It is envisioned that this research will identify the goal mathematical modeling could play in the Irish context for example; will it be used as a tool to learn mathematics (content), to develop mathematical modeling competencies (processes) in their own right or both. The research will explore perspectives of mathematical modeling that would work best in the Irish context and it will investigate teacher competencies needed to implement mathematical modeling in the primary classroom. The three research questions include; what are the goals of mathematical modeling in the Irish context; what theoretical framework of mathematical modeling would best fit the Irish context; and what teacher competencies are needed to implement mathematical modeling in the Irish primary classroom?

Discussion

It is proposed to answer three research questions to identify areas of support Irish teachers will require in the implementation of mathematical modeling in the Irish primary classroom. In order to accomplish this, it is suggested that a Collaborative Professional Inquiry model of TPL be formed with at least six participants where they engage in a six part programme of professional development over six months. The six parts include; establishment of a Collaborative Professional Inquiry, theory of mathematical modeling, practice and design of mathematical modeling tasks, theory and practice- implementation of mathematical modeling in classroom, assessment to inform practice- implementation of mathematical modeling in the classroom with a specific emphasis on formative assessment, reflection on theory and practice (of the implementation of mathematical modeling). Reflection will form a key role in data collection, so principles of Brookfield (1995), Rolfe (2001) and Gibbs (1988) will be integrated throughout the research. Data will be collected from multiple perspectives of the teacher, the group, the researcher/ professional development facilitator.

Conclusion

Proposed Methodology

Constructivism will embody this research where ontological assumptions will allow for multiple meanings and perspectives within historical and social context. An interpretive stance will be reported where the investigation will be “interested in the ways in which individuals and groups construct their world through their actions, beliefs and values” (Hamilton & Whittier, 2013, p. 27). This research will provide a case study at primary level in Ireland, which will lead curriculum innovation in implementing mathematical modeling to inform policy. Key conditions will be necessary for participants to partake in the Professional Collaborative Inquiry including; a learning culture promoted by leadership, external expertise (researcher), time for collaboration, teacher agency and voluntary participation (Kennedy, 2014; King, 2014). The TRU Framework by Schoenfeld (2017) will be adapted throughout the research as a reflective tool whereas, Guskey framework including Desimone core features will be used as an evaluative component. Both the core features of professional development and the transformative model of Collaborative Professional Inquiry can be evaluated in this research.

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